

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE RESEARCH OF NEWLYWED COUPLES' PRE-MARITAL EXPECTATIONS AND THE FULFILLMENT OF THESE EXPECTATIONS DURING THE MARRIAGE PROCESS IN KYRGYZSTAN

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to examine the pre-marital expectations of newlywed couples in Kyrgyzstan and explore how these expectations are fulfilled during the marriage process. In this study a qualitative research method was employed, using a case study model. The participants of the study voluntarily took part in the research. The study group consists of 16 individuals, including 12 women and 4 men, all married for a maximum of five years, from different regions of Kyrgyzstan. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews. The research data were analyzed using content analysis.

Keywords: Marriage, Expectation, expectations from marriage

Introduction

The family, as an institution, exerts a profound influence on an individual's life from birth to death, shaping not only physiological aspects but also economic, cultural, and social dimensions. It plays a crucial role in emotional development, personality formation, and behavioral guidance [1]. As the smallest unit of society, the family carries two fundamental meanings. The first refers to the family in which we are born and raised, the one that determines our place in the world and where we inherit our identity and legacy. The second refers to the family that individuals create through their own efforts, established through the institution of marriage. According to the modern perspective, marriage is an indispensable part of the formation of the family [2].

Marriage is more than a legal agreement; it is an emotional commitment in which spouses provide mutual support, navigate challenges together, and express love and devotion to one another. The decision to marry represents a shared promise to build a family, nurture children, support each other through life's disappointments, celebrate achievements, and embrace a shared journey [3].

People are social beings, and interpersonal relationships play a central role in their lives. Undoubtedly, marriage is one of the most important social relationships, as individuals have psychological, emotional, sexual, and spiritual expectations from it as a social institution. However, paradoxically, while marriage is expected to be the primary source of emotional and personal fulfillment for individuals, it is unfortunately experiencing its most fragile period today [4]. Perspectives, ideas, and opinions are key factors that shape an individual's attitude toward marriage. People's perceptions of marriage are closely tied to their expectations of it and the value they place on marriage and future

family relationships. Understanding these perspectives is essential, as marriage is not only a step toward forming a family but also a means of fulfilling material and emotional needs and establishing the foundation of society [5].

The role expectations of different individuals can vary widely. When starting a family, people may hold differing expectations about their roles and responsibilities. Research on the roles of young people can reveal these differences in role expectations. Achieving harmony between roles can increase satisfaction and lay a stronger foundation for a harmonious family life. Early recognition of these differences is critical to fostering healthy family relationships. Marriage role expectations encompass people's thoughts and views on how things should be or will be in marital relationships. There are two important aspects in this evaluation process: individuals form expectations regarding both their own roles and those of their partner. The expected roles in marriage can be divided into two categories: traditional and egalitarian. In traditional roles, male authority is considered dominant, and tasks and responsibilities in marriage are divided according to gender norms. In egalitarian roles, however, both men and women collaboratively discuss and share their duties and responsibilities, with the assumption of equal authority and decision-making in the relationship [6].

The degree of harmony in marriage depends on how realistic and compatible the expectations are. The closer both partners' expectations are to each other, the easier it is to achieve harmony. If the expectations of the husband and wife differ, problems are inevitable. For instance, if one partner wants children while the other does not, or if one partner expects a more romantic relationship while the other is unable to be romantic, such situations can lead to conflicts [7]. Expectations

affect the quality and duration of marriage. Research shows that marital expectations are universal. Since marriage is based on mutual expectations, unmet expectations often lead to challenges in relationships. People with differing expectations may experience less satisfaction and eventually grow distant from each other. Studies highlight that high and unrealistic expectations, when unmet, can be a cause of unhappiness [8].

Based on the literature review, the problem statement of this research is: "What are the pre-marital expectations of newlywed couples in Kyrgyzstan, and how are these expectations fulfilled during the marriage process?"

The aim of this research is to investigate the pre-marital expectations of newlywed couples in Kyrgyzstan and how these expectations are fulfilled during the marriage process.

Method

In this study, a qualitative research method using the case study model was employed. The study group consists of individuals who voluntarily participated in the research. It includes a total of 16 individuals, comprising 12 women and 4 men, all of whom have been married for a maximum of 5 years, and are from different regions of Kyrgyzstan. Data were collected using the semi-structured interview technique, a method designed to obtain in-depth information on specific topics.

Findings

The responses to the first research question, "What do you think a happy marriage is?" have been analyzed and are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Happy Marriage		
Participants	Responses	f
K1, K2, K3, K4, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K15, K16	Mutual understanding	14
K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K10, K11, K12, K13, K14, K15	Mutual love and respect	11
K4, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K16	Support Between Spouses	10
K1, K4, K14, K15	Attention	4
K5, K10, K6	Mutual trust	3
K1, K3, K5	Equality between spouses	3
K6, K7	Valuing each other	2

Upon examining Table 1, it is evident that nearly all participants (14 out of 16) emphasized the importance of "mutual understanding" between spouses as essential for a happy marriage. Participant K2 stated: "A happy marriage is when your spouse understands you perfectly." A significant majority of participants (11 out of 16) also highlighted that "love and respect" are necessary for a happy marriage. Participant K10 noted: "A happy marriage is a loving spouse." For many participants (10 out of 16), "support" between spouses was identified as a key element of marital happiness. As participant K6 explained: "A happy marriage

is when we always support each other and genuinely rejoice in each other's successes." Additionally, a few participants pointed out other factors such as "attention", "trust", and "equity between spouses" as indicators of a happy marriage. K3 remarked: "A happy marriage is not just about loving, understanding, and trusting each other; first, one must choose the right partner, because for a marriage to be happy, spouses must be equal to one another."

The responses to the second research question, "What were your expectations from marriage before you got married?" are analyzed in Table 2.

Table 2.

Expectations from Marriage		
Participants	Responses	f
K1, K4, K6, K7, K10, K14, K15, K16	Support and respect	8
K1, K2, K4, K5, K6, K9, K14	Understanding	7
K1, K3, K5, K10, K14, K15	Living in harmony and prosperity	6
K4, K5, K6, K7, K9, K14	Loving and being loved	6
K1, K3, K4, K7, K9, K15	Attention	6
K1, K5, K7, K9, K13	Improvement in quality of life	5
K11	Routine life	1

Table 2 reveals that half of the participants (8) primarily expect support and respect from marriage. K16: "My expectations from marriage were that my spouse and I would behave respectfully toward each other, support each other in everything, help each other, and overcome difficulties together." Some participants (7) also mentioned that, above all, they expected their spouses to be understanding. K2 stated: "My only expectation from marriage is that my spouse fully understands me." Some participants expressed expectations of living in

harmony and well-being, loving and being loved, and having their spouse show interest in them. K5 noted: "My expectation from marriage was mutual love." Some participants shared that before marriage, they expected to live separately from their spouse's parents, to be good parents to their future children, to live according to religious rules, and to see an improvement in their quality of life after marriage. K7: "I thought that after getting married, I wouldn't cook at home and would order food from a restaurant."

The responses to the question "How well were your expectations from marriage met after getting married?" which is the third question of the research, have been analyzed in Table 3.

Table 3.

Fulfillment of Expectations		
Participants	Responses	f
K2, K3, K4, K9, K12, K13, K15, K16	Fully fulfilled	8
K5, K6, K7, K10	Most expectations were fulfilled, but some aspects did not align	4
K11	Half of the expectations were fulfilled	1
K1	Most expectations were not fulfilled	1
K14	None of the expectations were fulfilled	1

Upon reviewing Table 3, it can be seen that half of the participants (8 out of 16) had their expectations from marriage fully met. K15: "My expectations before the marriage were completely fulfilled after I got married. In fact, my marriage is going even better than I expected." Four participants mentioned that their expectations were largely fulfilled, but there were some aspects that did not align. K6: "I made this decision consciously, so my expectations were generally correct. But, like most women, I probably expected to be given 24/7 attention, but unfortunately, that's impossible."

The remaining participants indicated varying levels of fulfillment: some felt that only half of their expectations were met, while others experienced unmet expectations or no fulfillment at all. K11: "My expectations from marriage were 50/50 fulfilled during the marriage process. Despite my fears that our relationship wouldn't be the same as before, after getting married, our relationship strengthened, and our trust in each other increased."

The responses to the question "How did your expectations before marriage affect your marriage process?" which is the fourth question of the research, have been analyzed in Table 4.

Table 4.

The Effect of Expectations on the Marriage Process		
Participants	Responses	f
K2, K4, K6, K7, K8, K10, K11, K12, K13, K14, K15	Did not affect	11
K3, K9, K16	Had a positive effect	3
K1, K5	Led to disappointment.	2

When Table 4 is examined, the vast majority of participants (11) stated that their expectations before marriage did not affect the marriage process at all. K4: "I don't think my expectations had any effect on my marriage." Some participants (3) mentioned that the fulfillment of their expectations during the marriage process positively affected their marriage. K16: "I believe my expectations had a positive effect on my marriage because all expectations and desires were discussed and understood beforehand. It was clear what we wanted and expected from each other, and this

greatly facilitated the marriage process." The remaining participants indicated that their expectations negatively affected their marriages and, in general, led to disappointment. K5: "I was disappointed as my expectations were not met, but apart from that, I don't think my expectations had any impact on my marriage."

The responses to the question "How did your responsibilities change after getting married?" which is the fifth question of the research, have been analyzed in Table 5.

Table 5.

Changes in Responsibilities		
Participants	Responses	f
K1, K2, K3, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K9, K10, K11, K12, K13, K14	Distribution of responsibilities between spouses according to social expectations	14
K1, K3, K4, K5, K6, K7, K8, K10, K11, K12, K14	The emergence of responsibilities for housework and childcare	11
K2, K9, K13	Taking on the responsibility for the family's financial situation.	3
K15, K16	Equal sharing of responsibilities.	2

In Table 5 it can be seen that the vast majority of participants (14) shared their marriage responsibilities with their spouses according to societal expectations after getting married. K11: "Not much changed. The entire financial upkeep of the house is my husband's responsibility. I continue to do tasks typically assigned to

women, like cleaning, cooking, and taking care of the children." K10: "I started spending more time creating warmth and comfort in the home. I try to conform to the behaviors expected of a wife in our society." Some participants (12) mentioned that after marriage, they had to take on the responsibilities of housework and

childcare. K7: "My responsibilities have increased significantly; the entire household upkeep and the children are now my responsibility."

Conclusion and discussion

When examining the indicators of a happy marriage, the vast majority of participants stated that couples should be understanding, a significant portion emphasized the importance of love and respect between spouses, and some mentioned that spouses should support each other, show appreciation, provide attention, and demonstrate trust. Additionally, the research concluded that for a marriage to be happy, certain variables are necessary, such as equality between spouses, living according to religious rules after marriage, having children, accepting each other as they are, being able to take responsibility, and creating shared memories together. In Özgüven's study conducted nearly 30 years ago, having children was considered an indicator of a happy marriage by almost half of the participants. However, in this study, only a small number of participants supported the same view. Therefore, this study does not align with the earlier literature on this aspect.[9]

When the findings related to marriage expectations are examined, it has been determined that most participants expect mutual support and respect from marriage, as well as understanding from their spouses. Some participants also expressed that they expect to live in harmony and well-being in marriage, to love and be loved, to receive attention from their spouses, and to experience an improvement in their quality of life. The remaining participants mentioned expectations such as living according to religious rules, having freedom of action, living separately from their spouse's parents, being good parents to their future children, as well as the possibility of life becoming routine after marriage and having no expectations from marriage at all. According to another study conducted among university students to examine marriage expectations, female students expressed a desire for their partner's religious beliefs to be similar to their own, while male students indicated that they expected their partner to be knowledgeable about and fulfill their religious duties.[10] In the results of our study, it was found that only a small number of participants included religion in their marriage expectations, so our study does not show consistency with the literature.

When examining the fulfillment of pre-marital expectations, it was found that most participants had their expectations fully met after marriage. Some participants reported that their expectations were largely met, although some discrepancies existed. A smaller group of participants indicated that only half of their expectations were fulfilled, while a few noted that their expectations were barely met or not met at all.

When the findings related to the impact of pre-marriage expectations on the marriage process are examined, the majority of participants indicated that their expectations had no effect on their marriage. Some participants mentioned that the fulfillment of their expectations during the marriage process positively affected

their marriage. However, some participants stated that their expectations negatively impacted their marriage and that, in general, they were disappointed. According to Devecioğlu [11], whether marriage expectations are met or not affects the marriage process. The fulfillment of expectations increases marital satisfaction, while unmet expectations decrease it. In the results of this study, participants stated that the fulfillment of their marriage expectations positively affected their marriage, while the lack of fulfillment negatively affected it. Therefore, the work conducted by Devecioğlu supports the findings of this study.

When the findings regarding changes in responsibilities after marriage are examined, the vast majority of participants stated that responsibilities were shared between spouses according to societal expectations after marriage. All female participants in the study reported taking on the responsibilities of housework and childcare after marriage, while all male participants stated that they took on the responsibility for the family's financial situation. A very small portion of participants mentioned that after marriage, they shared responsibilities equally, meaning both spouses were equally responsible for the family's financial situation and housework. In a study conducted by Bener [12], it was found that the expectations of female and male students regarding family and marital life differed from each other. It was concluded that female students held a more traditional perspective on family and marriage compared to male students. The clear conclusion drawn from this study is that gender roles play a significant role. Bener's study in Turkey revealed that young people have a traditional view of marriage, which supports the findings of this study.

There is a study that emphasizes the importance of spouses having the same attitudes, rather than an equal or traditional approach, when it comes to marital role expectations. The expectations of spouses regarding marital roles are of great importance in shaping their views on marriage. When spouses have similar expectations, the likelihood of conflict decreases, and marital harmony increases. On the contrary, in couples with opposing expectations, marital harmony tends to be lower, as one partner's expectations are not met. [13] When the opinions of the couples participating in this study were gathered, it was generally found that husbands and wives were in agreement about sharing responsibilities. Those who held traditional views expected women to handle housework and men to provide for the family. These couples reported being satisfied with their marriages, as these expectations were fulfilled after marriage.

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